

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "A Welfare Analysis of Policies Impacting Climate Change"

Johannes Emmerling¹ Frank Venmans² David Reinstein Ben Balmford

¹European Institute on Economics and the Environment, ²London School of Economics

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "A Welfare Analysis of Policies Impacting Climate Change". Both evaluators are strongly positive about this research. According to the first evaluator (Emmerling) the papers' main claims include a "clear ranking of climate-oriented policies", and the paper's results "are immediately very relevant for policymakers when deciding to implement or abandon given policies." Both offer substantive suggestions. Evaluator 2 (Venmans) provides several requests for clarification and emphasis, which may be particularly useful for policy-oriented readers less familiar with the MVPF public economics framework. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Johannes Emmerling](#)
2. [Frank Venmans](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Johannes Emmerling	91	4.0
Frank Venmans	90	4.9

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Johannes Emmerling

This is an excellent paper that makes significant contributions to climate policy evaluation. The authors' application of the MVPF framework to analyze 96 US environmental policies provides valuable insights that traditional cost-per-ton metrics often miss. The key contribution is to develop and meticulously apply the MVPF framework to a wide range of policies, that take into account all impacts on individuals and the public. This approach gives a very nice sufficient statistic in the overall efficiency of a wide range of policies, and allows [one to] easily ... compare and combine different policies. Also while the approach is marginal, it seems fairly well to [also] allow... for non-marginal policies (albeit this point would be good to illustrate and demonstrate more clearly). Besides specific points, one thing I also wonder is whether the "efficiency" from a social point of view of policies could also be compared across revenue generating and costing policies. For example, consider a MVPF of 1.5 for a subsidy vs. 0.5 for a tax: would these be considered similar in terms of social efficiency (as they differ similarly from 1 and zero, respectively)? But maybe using an average MVPF of revenues one would normalize all policies so they have the same "scale" in that overall efficiency can be measures on the same side of unity. But this is more of a suggestion or comment.

Finally [...] the framework starts out generally across individuals (and generations) indexed by i . One issue that I find missing is the distributional implications or heterogeneity effects. While it is at some points alluded to (and explicitly when taking the mean of marginal income or consumption), it would be good to indicate assumptions (and where relevant, whether this has been considered in the underlying studies) about distributional incidence. For instance, for EV subsidies it depends largely if uptake is mostly by rich households (potentially compared to a representative population, or poorer households). I don't mean to add this in the analytics but discuss assumptions and the issue where relevant.

Frank Venmans

Under which policy does a dollar of subsidy create the largest impact on welfare? Similarly, under which environmental tax does a dollar collected [...] create the lowest impact on welfare? The paper answers these questions by developing the Marginal Value of Public Funds (MVPF). This allows [one] to rank government policies according to their welfare impacts while respecting a given government budget.

The authors convincingly claim that their measure of the MVPF allows for a better ranking of public policies compared to standard measures of cost per tonne, be it the Resource cost per tonne, Government cost per tonne or Social cost per tonne. This is because the MVPF includes the role of inframarginal transfers which are [an] important part of policies, often of larger magnitude than the externalities that the policies correct for.

The strong point of the paper is to make the different components of the impacts of a policy additive and easy to distinguish. The paper builds on a very large body of literature, and builds on causal inference of the 18 most

The paper has also a novel way of estimating the social value of learning by doing, in a way that requires very [few] parameters. This makes it very policy-relevant. Overall, the paper does an extremely good job in giving an overview of all the effects of environmental policies over the last decades.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2		
	Johannes Emmerling		Frank Venmans		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	91	(78, 94)	90	(85, 94)	
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	96	(93, 100)	85	(80, 90)	
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁶	93	(90, 95)	86	(80, 90)	7
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁸	89	(79, 95)	85	(75, 95)	9
Logic & communication ¹⁰	80	(74, 86)	90	(80, 95)	
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹¹	65	(60, 70)	80	(75, 90)	12

Real-world relevance 13 , 14	93	(90, 96)	90	(85, 96)	
Relevance to global priorities 15 , 16	93	(90, 96)	90	(85, 96)	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2	
	Johannes Emmerling			Frank Venmans	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.0	(3.9, 4.3)		4.9	(4.7, 5.0)
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	4.0	(3.9, 4.1)	17	5.0	(4.3, 5.0)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim¹⁸	Belief in claim¹⁹	Suggested robustness checks²⁰	Important 'implication', policy, credibility²¹
Evaluator 1 Johannes Emmerling	"Clear ranking of climate-oriented policies with numbers up to 5" and "positive impact of revenue-generating policies... around 0.7" show "a very strong result"; the measure is "very salient and useful."	There is some uncertainty, but the important ones are discussed and shown, so overall of course some uncertainty but would say rather quite robust.	The robustness and importance of key variable notably SCC and VSL are important to highlight and their implications.	The findings in my view are immediately very relevant for policy makers when deciding to implement or abandon given policies.

(The second evaluator did not give a claim assessment.)

Evaluation manager's discussion (Ben Balmford)

"A Welfare Analysis of Policies Impacting Climate Change" offers a pioneering application of the Marginal Value of Public Funds (MVPF) framework to understanding the relative merits of climate related policy. Both evaluations are extremely positive, and highlight the utility of the paper for shaping policy responses. Broadly, this is driven by the fact that moving to MVPF rankings of different policy options allows policymakers to better assess options given the real-world constraints they face on budgets, and the wider impacts of policies through transfer effects. Both evaluators recognise the merit of this approach as compared with more common approaches to date. While there are numerous suggestions for ways to improve the paper, these are broadly about the exposition of the paper. As evaluator 1 suggests, a clear priority for further developing this agenda is in accounting for distributional impacts of policies, particularly as these can be so different across climate measures.

Issues meriting further evaluation²²

Most of the issues we mentioned in our managers' notes to the evaluators (see Google Doc [here](#)) could use further consideration. These include

The sensitivity of the marginal value of public funds (MVPF) estimates to alternative assumptions regarding the social cost of carbon (SCC), the generalizability of peer effects observed in specific contexts to other interventions and settings, publication bias, whether the MVPF framework fully accounts for inframarginal benefits, and issues of data and sample selection.

Unjournal process notes

Why we chose this paper

From our internal notes:

The synthesis/standardisation of a whole bunch of papers reporting impacts of various climate change policies could be very useful from an impact standpoint, particularly their ability to say something about heterogeneity.

[Important] implications for the allocation of resources to mitigate climate change.

The paper attempts to translate results on the impact of multiple climate policies into a common measure—the marginal value of public funds.

In doing so, the results of this paper are likely to be interpreted as “what we should do more of” as well as “what we should do less of”. It is almost surely important, then, to evaluate the strength of the key results of the paper.

Author engagement

The authors declined to respond to these evaluations, but noted they may wish to do so at a later date.

References

1. Hahn, R. W., Hendren, N., Metcalfe, R. D., & Sprung-Keyser, B. (2024). A Welfare Analysis of Policies Impacting Climate Change. *NBER Working Paper No. 32728*. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w32728>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↪](#)
2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↪](#)
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↪](#)
4. Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↪](#)

5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

6.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

7. The Marginal Value of Public Funds is not new, it exists in Public Economics, but the application to environmental economics is innovative. [↵](#)

8. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

9. Evaluating the welfare effects of environmental policies is intrinsically hard and will always come with large uncertainty intervals. Yet the paper does a very good job at synthesizing and reinterpreting the best information we have. [↵](#)

10. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

11.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↵](#)

12. Replicability has improved quite a bit in the last decade, this paper is no exception. [↵](#)

13.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

⇐

14.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" ⇐

15. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? ⇐

16.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" ⇐

17. This is clearly a top field, with some potential for a Top Econ one, if the method would be a tad clearer.

⇐

18.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. ⇐

19. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you **believe** the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. ↵

20.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. ↵

21.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important **implication** of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you **believe** this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

↵

22. Issues that may need further scrutiny, potentially by [“independent Unjournal evaluators”](#) and in future replication and robustness-checking exercises. ↵